

EFFECT OF PHYSICAL AGING ON VISCOELASTIC RESPONSE OF MULTI-PHASE RUBBER-TOUGHENED EPOXIES

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ABSTRACT

Rubber-toughened epoxies are commonly used for many structural applications to overcome brittleness in neat epoxy resins. The two phase morphology produces great improvements in fracture resistance with a minor reduction in other physical and mechanical properties. This study focuses on the physical aging response of a model rubber toughened epoxy at different rubber contents. Both creep and stress relaxation experiments were performed to probe the aging response in the temperature range below the glass transition of the epoxy, but above that of the rubber phase. A time - aging time superposition was observed for samples containing up to 10 wt.% rubber in the creep compliance experiments. However, in the stress relaxation experiments, the superposition between time and aging time was no longer observed. In fact, at longer aging times in stress relaxation the rubber toughened samples exhibit a lower modulus than at short aging times. Possible reasons for the discrepancies are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The physical aging response of amorphous polymers has been extensively studied in both creep and stress relaxation experiments performed after a temperature jump from above the glass transition to below it. It is widely accepted (Struik, 1978; Lee and McKenna, 1988, 1990; Matsuoka, 1994) that a time-aging time superposition principle adequately describes the changes in viscoelastic response that accompany the evolution of the nonequilibrium thermodynamic properties of the polymer. On the other hand, there has been relatively little experimentation to study the physical aging response of two phase amorphous polymers such as rubber toughened epoxies (McDonnough, et al, 1992). In this paper we report results from a study of the physical aging response in stress relaxation and creep experiments for a series of rubber toughened epoxies at temperatures between the T_g of the rubber phase and that of the epoxy resin and at rubber contents up to 10 %. Surprisingly, while time-aging time superposition well describes the response of the neat resin and the rubber toughened systems in the creep experiments, it is found that in stress relaxation conditions, the time-aging time superposition cannot be applied for the rubber toughened material. The results are tentatively interpreted in terms of changing stress and strain distributions in a viscoelastic composite material.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials

The epoxy resin used in this study was a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DOW DER 332) cured with an amine terminated polypropylene oxide (Jeffamine D400 from Texaco Chemical Co.) to form a network. The molar ratio of epoxide to amine was stoichiometric. The elastomer used to

toughen the epoxy network was a carboxyl-terminated random copolymer of butadiene and acrylonitrile, CTBN, (Goodrich Hycar 1300x8).

The mixture of epoxy resin, amine hardener, and elastomer was stirred by hand on a 60 °C heated hot plate until clear. The mixture was then degassed for 10 minutes at 35 °C and cast into a mold to make dumbbell-shaped samples. The samples were cured at 100 oC for 24 hours and slowly cooled in oven to room temperature overnight. The dimensions of the test specimens were 19 x 165 x 3.2 mm (3/4 x 6.5 x 1/8 inch) with gauge section of 12.7 x 38 mm (1/2 x 1.5 inch). The specimens were kept in a sealed desiccator prior to performing the physical aging experiments(several weeks).

The glass transition temperatures for the epoxy network toughened with different amount of CTBN rubber were determined in heating using a differential scanning calorimeter (Perkin - Elmer DSC-7) at 20 °C/min. Two glass transition temperatures were observed, the values were 4 °C and 37 °C representing the rubber particles and the epoxy matrix, respectively. The glass transition temperature for the epoxy matrix is slightly lower than the value obtained for the neat epoxy resin (~ 42.4 °C) reported previously.

Physical Aging Experiments

Mechanical testing was performed using a computer-controlled servo-hydraulic testing machine (Instron model 132.25), equipped with an oven for temperature control. The temperature was controlled using a Cole-Parmer Digi-sense model 2186-20 temperature controller. Measurements of the temperature between the top and bottom of the sample showed that the gradient was less than 0.2 °C. Oven stability was better than ± 0.1 °C during each experiment. The dumbbell-shaped specimens were first annealed for 30 minutes at 22 °C above the T_g of the epoxy matrix and then placed in the testing machine at the testing temperature where the rubber-toughened epoxy glasses began to age. In what follows we examine results for two aging temperatures: 25 and 33 °C, which are above the glass transition temperature of the rubber phase, but below that of the epoxy phase. The mechanical tests were carried out in uniaxial extension under both stress relaxation and creep conditions. Deformations or loads were applied sequentially at aging times *t* that doubled with each test, i.e., *t* = 30 min., 60 min., 120 min., etc.. Zero aging time is defined as the time at which the sample was placed into the test machine. The duration *t*_i of the deformation/load application was varied so that the ratio *t*_i/*t* was constant throughout the aging experiment. The value of *t*_i/*t* used in this study was 0.025. In the stress relaxation experiments, the strain used was 0.25% as measured by an extensometer with gauge length of 1.00 inch. For the creep experiments, the engineering stress applied to the samples was 2 MPa and the strain was measured with an extensometer attached to the specimen. The stress relaxation modulus *E*(*t*) at any measured time *t* after the imposition of the strain was calculated as $E(t) = \sigma(t) / \epsilon$. Similarly the creep compliance *D*(*t*) was calculated as $D(t) = \epsilon(t) / \sigma$.

Method of Analysis

Each stress relaxation and creep compliance curve was analyzed by using Kohlrausch-Williams-Watts (KWW) (Kolrausch, 1849;Williams and Watts, 1976) stretched exponential function with three fitting parameters:

$$E(t) = E_0 \exp [-(t/\tau_r)^{\beta_r}] \quad (1)$$

$$D(t) = D_0 \{ 1 + \exp (t/\tau_c)^{\beta_c} \} \quad (2)$$

Where *E*₀ is the zero time relaxation modulus, 2*D*₀ is the zero-time compliance, *τ_r* and *τ_c* are the characteristic relaxation and retardation times, respectively. *β_r* and *β_c* are shape parameters and indicate the non-exponentiality of the viscoelastic response. The SigmaPlot (Jandel Scientific, 1994) non-linear least-square curve-fitting routine was used for the analysis of the data for each experimental condition. If the stress relaxation curves obtained at different aging time are obey the time-aging time superposition principle, then values of *E*₀ and *β_r* must be the same at different aging times. Similarly, the creep compliance curves at different aging times must have the same

D_0 and β_C to allow a time-aging time superposition. If we have time-aging time superposition, the aging time shift factor, a_{te} , in terms of the KWW function is defined as:

$$a_{te} = \tau(te) / \tau(te,ref) \quad (3)$$

where $\tau(te)$ is the value of the characteristic relaxation or retardation time [equations (1) and (2)] at the aging time te and $\tau(te,ref)$ is the value at the reference aging time. We note that often time-aging time superposition requires a slight vertical shift as well as the horizontal one (Struik, 1978). This would correspond to a constant multiplying E_0 or D_0

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Creep

Figure 1, depicts the effect of aging on the creep response of the DGEBA/D400 diamine glass without any rubber at 1 MPa at aging temperatures of 33 oC. From the plot, we observe that the creep responses shift towards longer times with increasing aging time te . The aging time shift factors a_{te} necessary to do the superposition with a reference aging time was determined by using Equation (3) to fit the data. For the data shown in Fig. (1), the individual creep curves could be superimposed with best-fit value of c equal to 0.28. Figures 2 and 3, show the creep response curves for the DGEBA/D-400 diamine glasses containing 5 wt.% and 10 wt.% of CTBN rubber, respectively. For these data, the applied engineering stress was 2 MPa and the aging temperature was 25 oC. Similar to previous results (Lee and McKenna, 1988) the individual creep curves could be superimposed by the horizontal shifting along the time axis. However, the values of c for the rubber toughened material differ from that of the neat resin. The value of c decreases as the amount of CTBN increases. Importantly, the viscoelastic response of each curve was verified to be linear by calculating the unload portion of the curve from the loading portion of the curve using the Boltzmann Superposition.

Stress Relaxation

Similar to the creep experiments, the step-strain stress relaxation responses in physical aging conditions were examined for the same epoxy glasses containing CTBN rubber. In Figure 4, the relaxation modulus curves are plotted for increasing aging times for the neat DGEBA/D400 resin at 33 oC (About 9 oC below the DSC measured T_g). The relaxation modulus curves were fitted with Equation (1). Again, for time - aging time to be valid, the values of r must be the same at different aging times. It is readily apparent that these curves measured at different aging times can be superposed by shifting along the time axis and the r value for this set of data was found to be 0.30. Hence, as found previously (Lee and McKenna), the time - aging time superposition appears to be valid for this glass network.

The stress-relaxation modulus curves at different aging times for samples containing CTBN rubber are depicted in Figures 5 and 6. Unlike the sample containing no CTBN rubber, shown in Figure (4), the values of E_0 and r vary for the different aging times. Therefore, the time - aging time superposition is no longer valid for these samples. In Figure 7, we show only the relaxation modulus curves at 30 min. and 16 hours of aging for a sample containing 10 wt.% CTBN rubber. It is clear from the figure the classical time - aging time superposition principle is no longer valid for these two phase network glasses. Interestingly, the sample aged for the longer time has a lower value of modulus over most of the relaxation than does the newly quenched sample. Again, each set of data was found to be within the linear viscoelastic range by comparison of the response in the unloading segment of the experiment with the Boltzmann superposition.

DISCUSSION

After quenching a material from above the glass transition to below it, the system is out of equilibrium and the volume and enthalpy evolve spontaneously towards equilibrium in a process known as structural recovery (McKenna, 1989). Associated with the structural recovery are changes in mechanical properties that have come to be known as physical aging (Struik, 1978). When a rubbery phase, which is in equilibrium, is mixed with a glassy phase (nonequilibrium) one

would not anticipate that the rubbery phase would contribute to the structural recovery of the system. Hence, the aging should be determined by the glassy phase. The surprising result reported above, that the aging behavior of the rubber toughened epoxy in stress relaxation experiments differs dramatically from that observed in the creep experiments, is difficult to explain. It was expected that, because the rubber itself should not age, the response would be that of the neat resin. Yet, we observe that the influence of the structural recovery that occurs in the epoxy phase seems to be different depending upon whether it is probed by stressing the sample or straining it. Here we pose some potential reasons and discuss them.

The observation that the neat resin ages in virtually the same fashion in both stress relaxation and creep conditions leads one away from experimental artifacts such as thermally induced stress gradients through the sample (LeGrand, 1995) as an explanation for the observations. This is particularly so since the temperature conditions were nearly the same for the neat and rubber modified systems. Furthermore, the observation that the compliances obtained at different aging times can be superimposed by simple horizontal shifts while the moduli cannot is not readily explained by nonlinear effects, particularly since the individual curves were found to follow Boltzmann superposition. Hence, one is led to the possibility that it is simply the two phase nature of the material that leads to this apparently anomalous behavior. Unfortunately, there are few analyses of the expected viscoelastic response of two phase systems, well enough of aging effects on them. A possible partial explanation of these results is, however, found in the analysis of Brinson and Knauss (1990, 1991). They performed a two dimensional finite element analysis of the dynamic response of a system of an array of viscoelastic cylinders embedded in a viscoelastic matrix and compared the finite element analysis to the bounds that would be expected from composite mixing rules that assumed either uniform stress or uniform strain in the system. Interestingly, depending on the relative magnitudes and relaxation times of the cylinder and matrix moduli, it was found that the response with frequency could change from one bound to another. Obviously such complicated behavior may explain why we see an apparent anomaly in the rubber toughened epoxy. Does one have constant stress or strain in the system? Does the distribution change when one goes from creep to stress relaxation? In addition, it is possible that there are bulk modulus effects that might play a role in the two phase system. The rubber toughened epoxies probably need to be treated in a fully three dimensional analysis because they are systems of rubber spheres which are surrounded by the epoxy matrix. In beginning the series of experiments, we anticipated that the rubbery phase would have no impact on the aging and that the epoxy system would age. This, perhaps naively, assumes that working above the T_g of the rubber results in the rubber relaxation time being extremely short with a resulting vanishingly small load supported by the rubber phase. This is true for the shear response of the rubber. However, in the three dimensional system, it is likely that bulk relaxations (Hence the finite compressibility of the rubber) will be important. In this case, the bulk modulus of the rubber is only about $1/3$ to $1/2$ that of the glassy matrix (cf. Immergut, 1990; McKenna, 1989) and the response becomes a mixture of that of the rubbery and the glassy phases. Further, densification of the glassy matrix during the aging experiment changes the system internal stress distribution. This would further complicate the behavior calculated by Brinson and Knauss (1990, 1991) and might provide an explanation as to why the creep and stress relaxation responses are so different in the aging experiments. In the future, we will be performing finite element analyses to establish how the different aspects of the viscoelastic response of such two phase materials can affect their creep, relaxation and aging behaviors.

SUMMARY

In this study, we have examined the physical aging responses of CTBN rubber toughened epoxy thermoset glasses at temperatures above the T_g of the rubber but below that of the epoxy. It was found that classical time - aging time superposition was obeyed for both toughened (two-phase) and untoughened (one phase) epoxy in the creep experiments. For stress relaxation, the superposition of time and aging time was no longer valid for the samples containing CTBN rubber. Such apparently anomalous results are not readily explained either in terms of thermally induced stresses nor as non-linear effects in the filled systems. It is proposed that the composite nature of the two-phase system might lead to differences in the viscoelastic responses either due to a change in behavior from a uniform stress to a uniform strain state in the material or to bulk relaxations in the rubber affecting response in relaxation (constant deformation) experiments differently from the response in creep (constant stress) experiments. Further experiments and finite element analysis are underway.

Figure 1. Creep compliance curves for DGEBA/D-400 diamine glass at aging temperature of 33 °C at aging times ranged from 0.5 hours to 67.1 hours. The applied engineering stress is 1 PMa.

Figure 2. Creep compliance curves for DGEBA/D-400 diamine glass containing 5 wt.% of CTBN rubber. The aging temperature is 25 °C and aging times ranged from 0.5 hours to 16 hours. The applied engineering stress is 2 MPa.

Figure 3. Creep compliance curves for DGEBA/D-400 diamine glass containing 10 wt.% of CTBN rubber. The aging temperature is 25 °C and aging times ranged from 0.5 hours to 16 hours. The applied engineering stress is 2 MPa.

Figure 4. Stress relaxation modulus curves for DGEBA/D400 diamine glass at aging temperature of 33 °C. The aging times ranged from 0.5 hours to 4 hours. The applied strain is 0.2%.

Figure 5. Stress relaxation modulus curves for DGEBA/D400 diamine glass containing 5 wt.% CTBN rubber. The aging temperature is 25 °C. The aging times ranged from 0.5 hours to 16 hours. The applied strain is 0.25 %.

Figure 6. Stress relaxation modulus curves for DGEBA/D400 diamine glass containing 10 wt.% CTBN rubber. The aging temperature is 25 °C. The aging times ranged from 0.5 hours to 16 hours. The applied strain is 0.25%

10wt% CTBN/EPOXY at 25 C

Figure 7. Stress relaxation modulus curves for DGEBA/D400 diamine glass containing 10 wt.% CTBN rubber. The aging temperature is 25 °C. The aging times shown at 0.5 hours and 16 hours. The applied strain is 0.25%.